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THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE DISCIPLINE LABOR AND THE METHODOLOGY OF ITS TEACHING AND THE MAIN TASKS OF THEIR SOLUTION

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ABSTRACT

Labor education begins in the family - we have already talked about this more than once. But school also has a significant influence on the education of a young person. For schoolchildren, labor is a necessary and important means of developing moral ideas and personality traits. The goal of labor education of schoolchildren is the formation of a natural physiological and intellectual need for labor. At school, it is closely connected with the polytechnic training of students, which ensures the level of knowledge of the basics of technology and organization of production.

Key words. *Formation of creative and technical skills in the process of professional training of future teachers, technology, labor training, education.*

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ДИСЦИПЛИНЫ ТРУД И МЕТОДИКА ЕГО ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ И ОСНОВНЫЕ ЗАДАЧИ ИХ РЕШЕНИЕ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Трудовое воспитание начинается в семье – об этом мы говорили уже ни раз. Но школа также имеет весомое влияние на воспитание юной личности. Для школьников труд – необходимое и важное средства развитие нравственных

представлений и качеств личности. Цель трудового воспитания школьников – формирование естественной физиологической и интеллектуальной потребности в труде. В школе оно, тесно связано с политехнической подготовкой учащихся, что обеспечивает уровень знания основ техники и организации производства.

Ключевые слова. *Формирование, творческо-технических умений, в процессе, профессиональной подготовки, будущих учителей, технология, трудового обучения, воспитания.*

Labor education begins in the family - we have already talked about this more than once. But school also has a significant influence on the education of a young person. For schoolchildren, labor is a necessary and important means of developing moral ideas and personal qualities. The goal of labor education for schoolchildren is to form a natural physiological and intellectual need for work. At school, it is closely connected with the polytechnic training of students, which ensures the level of knowledge of the basics of technology and organization of production.

Within the walls of a comprehensive school, labor education solves several basic and important tasks:

- Motivation for work, stimulation of interest in knowledge, the need for work as a creative process, the desire for practical activities;
- Formation of a positive attitude towards work in schoolchildren;
- Education of moral qualities: a sense of duty, hard work, responsibility, mutual assistance, determination, perseverance, honesty;
- Development of creative abilities of students by means of manual labor;
- Mastering by schoolchildren of various types of techniques, labor skills, formation of an internal culture of physical and mental labor.

Involvement of children in work must be carried out taking into account the physiology of children of primary school age, the characteristics of their body and psyche, their interests and abilities. By engaging in work, students enter into relationships with objects, means, results of work, the work itself, and interpersonal relationships with participants in the work. Personal qualities are formed on the basis of the relationships that arise in work[2].

Formation of attitudes to the subject of labor deepens the ecological, moral education of students, creates conditions for the development of the aesthetic culture of the individual. Thus, it contributes to the harmonious development of the individual, whose activity is distinguished by creative and constructive work. Attitudes to the means of labor arise as a result of the use of technology, equipment, tools for processing the subject of labor, with the purpose of creating a product.

Based on the emerging attitudes to the means of labor, primary school students develop a careful attitude to tools, personal belongings, school property, and public property. These attitudes are manifested in accuracy, discipline, and attentiveness. The process of processing the object of labor with the help of the means of labor ends with a material result, the substantive value of which is determined by its appropriateness, ease of use, and beauty. Forming an attitude to the result of labor is of particular importance for developing primary school students' accuracy, discipline, responsibility for the task at hand, and a careful attitude to the results of human labor.

As a result of the emerging attitudes of primary school students to the labor process itself, the concept of labor as the only source of welfare of society and the condition for the development and formation of personality is formed. The attitude of students to the labor process is of great importance for the formation of such personal qualities as patience, diligence, attentiveness, fairness, conscientiousness, organization, purposefulness, hard work, discipline, self-criticism. The attitude to oneself as a subject of labor activity that arises in work develops self-confidence and responsibility in primary school students. Labor provides an opportunity to check and receive an objective reflection of the existing capabilities of students, to realize the importance of the self-education process in the formation of personal qualities. Labor activity ensures self-education and self-development of the strengths and abilities of students, forms their consciousness and self-awareness, while acting as the most important factor in the formation of the "I" of the child's personality[5].

In work activity, a number of influences can be distinguished: of an individual on an individual; of an individual on a group; of a group on an individual; of a group on a group. Interpersonal relations arising in the work activity of primary school students contribute to the implementation of the process of socialization of the individual. In collective work activity, schoolchildren have to coordinate their goals with the goals of the group, to connect their efforts with the efforts of other participants in joint work. A dependence arises between personal and public interests, as a result of which the public goals of the activity and the direction of the individual, collective management of activity and self-management of behavior, organization of collective work activity and self-organization, the content of work activity and personal work experience, the formation of a group and the education of an individual in it are linked together.

Organizational forms of labor education and training are chosen by the teacher. In order for labor to become a favorite thing, the child must experience the success and joy of labor. Therefore, it is advisable to build training at the highest, accessible level of difficulty; experiencing the joy of deserved labor success, the young person acquires a sense of self-worth, pride in his work[4].

Methodology of teaching technology is a pedagogical science, which is an application of the principles of didactics to the teaching of the subject technology. Methodology of teaching technology, like any science, has its own subject of research, that is, a certain area of reality. Recently, special attention has been paid not only to the training and education of students, but also to their development, therefore, the subject of methodology of teaching technology should be understood as the theory and practice of teaching technology, education and development of students in the process of teaching technology.

Like any science, the methodology of teaching technology has its own research methods, with the help of which the process of scientific research activity in the field of teaching technology is carried out. These include both theoretical and experimental methods. Based on the above, the methodology of teaching technology is a humanitarian, applied (not fundamental) science. The task of the methodology of teaching technology is to find answers to the following questions:

- Why teach?
- What to teach?
- How to teach technology?

The answer to the first question is determined by the formulation of the learning objectives. Learning objectives in general and the learning objectives of technology in particular are determined by the social order of society. The content (what to teach) is directly dependent on the learning objectives. For example, if the goal is to form a scientific worldview in students, then the content of the technology course must include material of a worldview nature. Since the goals of technological education change over time, the content of the technology course also undergoes changes. The content is also influenced by the psychological characteristics of students, as well as the level of development of the information environment.

Education is the process and result of mastering a certain system of knowledge in the interests of a person, society and the state; a specially organized system of conditions and educational, methodological and scientific bodies and institutions in society, necessary for human development.

Training is a specially organized, controlled process of interaction between teachers (teaching) and students (learning), aimed at mastering knowledge, skills and abilities, forming a worldview, developing the mental strength and potential of students, developing and consolidating self-education skills in accordance with the set goals[1].

Education is the process and result of the teacher's purposeful influence on the student's personality for his/her maximum development, his/her entry into the context

of modern culture, becoming a subject of his/her own life, forming his/her motives and values.

Development is the process of a natural change in the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the personality as a result of a person's mastering experience that corresponds to the socio-historical conditions in which he/she lives, age and individual characteristics of his/her psyche[3].

Knowledge is facts, theories, information about nature, man, society, taken in the aspect of the result of their assimilation.

Skills are readiness for practical and theoretical actions performed quickly and accurately under the control of consciousness.

Skills are actions brought to automatism, formed by repeated exercises.

The goal of learning is a conscious way of anticipating the result of learning. There are didactic (educational, training), educational and developmental goals.

The content of learning is a system of scientific knowledge, skills and abilities, relationships and experience of creative activity, transmitted in the learning process.

Forms of learning are a way of implementing the educational process, an external expression of the coordinated interaction of the teacher and students, carried out in a certain order and mode (lesson, excursion, consultation, seminar, elective, lecture, etc.) [6].

Method of teaching is a system of consistent, interconnected actions of the teacher and students, ensuring the assimilation of the content of education, the development of mental powers and abilities of students, their mastery of the means of self-development and self-study.

Teaching tools are material objects and objects of spiritual culture intended for the organization and implementation of the educational process.

Interrelated forms, methods and means of teaching make up the technology of teaching. The methodology of teaching technology is closely related to other sciences.

The methodology of teaching technology is connected, on the one hand, with pedagogy, psychology, with social and humanitarian sciences in general, on the other hand, with technical sciences. Naturally, the methodology of teaching technology as a branch of pedagogical knowledge is connected, and "vitaly" connected, with pedagogical sciences and, first of all, with didactics. As already noted, it grows out of didactics and is based on its basic provisions. In turn, didactics uses the results of research in methodological sciences, generalizing them, establishes general patterns of learning processes.

The methodology of teaching technology is connected with the general theory and methodology of education. The methodology examines the problems of education

using the example of research into the educational aspect, the educational influence of the process of teaching technology on the development of the student's personality[7].

A major role in the development of the methodology of teaching technology is played by its connection with psychology. It is manifested in relations with a whole set of psychological sciences. The methodology of teaching technology is connected with general psychology. The latter reveals the nature and essence of mental activity, its basic forms, the laws of its origin and development. General psychology is a natural scientific basis that determines the educational influences on the development of the student's personality, which are carried out in the process of teaching technology.

For the methodology of teaching technology, it is very important to rely on the characteristics of the mental development of children and young people, that is, on age psychology. When developing forms and methods of teaching technology, one cannot help but take into account the issues of psychology of training and education. Here, the connection of the methodology with educational psychology is manifested. Defining the content of training, which includes knowledge and skills in the technology of processing materials, energy and information, the methodology establishes links with labor psychology and engineering psychology. The connection of the methodology of teaching technology with other social and humanitarian sciences allows us to solve problems of education in the process of teaching technology, the development of socially significant qualities of the student's personality[8-9].

The other side of the connections is the connections with technical sciences. They allow the methodology to solve the problem of developing the content of technology training. The content of training, that is, the educational material that is selected for study in the school course of technology, is drawn from the technology of structural materials, mechanical engineering, technical mechanics, electrical and radio engineering and other general technical and special technical disciplines. Through technical sciences, the methodology of teaching technology is connected with natural science disciplines, primarily with physics, as well as mathematics. This is due to the fact that technical sciences organically include physical and other natural science concepts, as well as mathematical apparatus. Therefore, the study of technical sciences without connection with physics, mathematics and other disciplines is impossible.

This is the system of connections between the methodology of teaching technology and other sciences. It is very important to note here that the considered connections between the methodology of teaching technology and socio-economic and technical sciences underlie the entire system of professional and pedagogical training of a technology teacher. And the methodology of teaching technology is a system-forming element of this training[10].

Answering the question of how to teach technology, we choose the organizational forms of training, methods and means of its implementation that correspond to the goals and specific content. For example, if the goals are set for developing research skills in students, then in the process of teaching technology it is necessary to organize appropriate laboratory and experimental work, use research methods of teaching, the necessary teaching aids (devices, tools, information sources, etc.). The choice of forms, methods and means of teaching is also influenced by the level of development of psychological, pedagogical and natural sciences, as well as engineering and technology.

Thus, the goals, content, forms, methods and means of teaching form a methodological system in which the leading role is played by the goals of training, determining the strategy of pedagogical activity. Let us consider the conceptual and terminological apparatus.

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